

A Benders decomposition approach for solving a two-stage local energy market problem under uncertainty

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ABSTRACT

New consumer-centric electricity market schemes have emerged as an alternative to manage the energy balancing locally in distribution networks with high distributed energy resources (DERs) penetration. Peer-to-peer (P2P) energy trading has become an attractive scheme for reducing user and distribution system operators (DSO) costs through the energy surplus exchange between the energy community users, where the uncertainty of DERs and the consumption are challenging issues that require suitable managing for a proper market operation. This article presents a novel two-stage stochastic mixed-integer linear programming model to address the scheduling day-ahead problem of an energy community operating under a P2P energy trading scheme. The formulation proposed minimizes the expected community cost considering the network limitations, ensuring fair trading in the local energy market (LEM), and allowing the prosumers to act as buyers or sellers depending on their load consumption and self-generation. In order to reduce the shared information by consumers/prosumers that trade energy, the proposed model is decomposed into a master problem (MP) and subproblems (SPs) to manage the network constraints and the market requirements, respectively. With this purpose, the Benders decomposition approach is implemented using the recently introduced Strengthened Benders cuts to address the binary variables related to the market and battery operation in the SPs. The model and the algorithm are tested in the 69-bus radial distribution system, considering from 3 to 39 agents trading energy to measure the model scalability. In this analysis, the algorithm convergence shows that the proposed methodology reduces the LEM's shared information without increasing the energy community cost.

1. Introduction

The constant decrease in the prices of distributed generation (DG) is allowing residential users to opt for small-scale self-generation and energy storage systems (ESS), providing them greater autonomy and control over electricity consumption. This new paradigm of more active, aware, and empowered users has prompted a rethinking of the residential distribution networks (DN) to face future energy communities (ECs) with high penetration of distributed energy resources (DERs) and eventual ECs operating under a transactive energy (TE) scheme [1]. Peer-to-Peer (P2P) energy trading is one of the potential emerging alternative schemes to model this paradigm and increase the efficiency in an EC with high DERs penetration and users willing to sell their energy surplus to other community users in an eventual local energy market (LEM) [2]. Thus, many research papers have addressed the challenge of modeling these new consumer-centric TE schemes over the last years to study their benefits and proper operation.

1.1. Literature review

Different techniques have been applied in the P2P energy trading field to promote user energy sharing, establish the local market pricing, and manage users' private information. We refer the reader to [3] and [4] for a recent and comprehensive review of related academic papers, classification

and techniques, and industrial applications in P2P energy trading.

In what follows, we review more recent works on P2P trading and group them into deterministic and stochastic approaches to highlight the differences between the methods.

1.1.1. Deterministic approaches

A P2P energy trading model is addressed in [5] under a centralized market design, where a coordinator has complete control over the community batteries and seeks to minimize grid operation costs. However, network technical constraints, such as the balance equations in nodes and lines, including the reactive power effect and the voltage limit operation, are not considered in that work, which might lead to infeasible or impractical solutions for real cases. In this regard, centralized markets usually entail that the coordinator has access to users' information, which restricts users' autonomy and privacy.

Decentralized markets are an alternative to keep users' autonomy and privacy. Those markets have been addressed, for example, in [6, 7, 8, 9, 10]. The work in [6] proposes a deterministic TE framework for trading energy between prosumers with Battery Energy Storage System (BESS) and DG and seeks to maximize the community surplus. In the same research direction, a decentralized P2P energy trading model is presented in [7], which uses the primal-dual gradient method to manage the trading scheme. This deterministic model includes technical constraints through the Power Transfer Distribution Factor (PTDF); however, the

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Nomenclature

Sets

- $i \in \mathcal{B}$ Set of buses
 $i \in \mathcal{A}$ Set of agents/users that trade energy in the local energy market, such that $\mathcal{A} \subset \mathcal{B}$
 $t \in \mathcal{T}$ Set of time slots.
 $s \in \mathcal{S}$ Set of scenarios.
 $(i, j) \in \mathcal{L}$ Set of lines, such that $\mathcal{L} = \{(i, j); i, j \in \mathcal{B}\}$.

Parameters

- $PG_{t,s}^{max}$ Maximum active power output at period t in scenario s [%].
 $PL_{i,t,s}$ Active load of bus i at period t in scenario s [kW].
 $QL_{i,t,s}$ Reactive load of bus i at period t in scenario s [kvar].
 V^{min} Minimum voltage allowed [p.u.].
 V^{max} Maximum voltage allowed [p.u.].
 $BS_{i,j}$ Non-zero upper diagonal bus admittance matrix elements [p.u.].
 $S_{i,j}^{max}$ Allowed maximum apparent power of the line between buses i and j [kVA].
 $G_{i,j}, B_{i,j}$ Conductance and susceptance of the line between buses i and j such that $i \neq j$ [p.u.].
 G_i, B_i Conductance and susceptance of the line between buses i and j such that $i = j$ [p.u.].
 DG_i PV system capacity in bus i [%].
 SOC^{min} Minimum state of charge of battery [%].
 SOC^{max} Maximum state of charge of battery [%].
 φ^{ch} Charging battery efficiency [%].
 φ^{ds} Discharging battery efficiency [%].
 PB Maximum charge/discharge power for battery i in a period [kW].
 BT Battery capacity [kWh].
 Δt Time slot. (1 h in the model).
 M Big M.
 κ^{max} Maximum substation power.
 $\lambda_{t,s}^{bg}$ Price of the energy bought from the grid at time t in scenario s .
 λ^{sg} Feed in Tariff or net metering price.
 ρ_s Probability of the scenario s .

First stage variables

- κ_t^{bg} Energy bought from the grid through the substation at period t [kW]
 κ_t^{sg} Energy sold to the grid through the substation at period t [kW]

Second stage variables

- $\Delta p_{i,t,s}$ Difference between the energy self-generated and the consumption in bus i at period t in scenario s [kW].
 $p_{i,t,s}$ Energy self-generated in bus i at period t in scenario s [kW].
 $p_{i,t,s}^{bg}$ Energy bought from the grid by the bus i at the period t in scenario s [kW].
 $p_{i,t,s}^{sg}$ Energy sold to the grid by the bus i at the period t in scenario s [kW].
 $p_{i,t,s}^{bm}$ Energy bought from the market by the bus i at the period t in scenario s [kW].
 $p_{i,t,s}^{sm}$ Energy sold to the market by the bus i at the period t in scenario s [kW].
 $q\kappa_{i,t,s}^{bg}$ Reactive power bought from the grid through the substation of bus i at period t in scenario s [kvar].
 $v_{i,t,s}$ Voltage of bus i at period t in scenario s [p.u].
 $\theta_{i,t}$ Angle of bus i at period t in scenario s , such that $\Delta\theta_{i,s}^{i,j} = (\theta_{i,t,s} - \theta_{j,t,s})$ is a summary expression of the angle difference between bus i and bus j .
 $p_{i,s}^{i,j}$ Active power in line between buses i and j at period t in scenario s [kW].
 $q_{i,s}^{i,j}$ Reactive power in line between buses i and j at period t in scenario s [kvar].
 $ch_{i,t,s}$ Power charged by the battery in the bus i at period t in scenario s [kW].
 $ds_{i,t,s}$ Power discharged by the battery in the bus i at period t in scenario s [kW].
 $soc_{i,t,s}$ State of charge of battery of bus i at period t in scenario s [kWh].
 $w_{i,t,s}$ Binary variable: 1 if the battery is charging in bus i at period t in scenario s , 0 otherwise.
 $y_{i,t,s}$ Binary variable: 1 if the agent in bus i at period t in scenario s has an energy surplus, 0 otherwise.

BESS and DG are not modeled explicitly, rather only the energy shortage or surplus is considered an input parameter. On its part, a dual decomposition method is proposed in [8] to coordinate the interaction between multi-regional prosumers under a P2P energy trading scheme maximizing the social welfare and including the voltage levels and the reactive power; however, batteries are not considered in the formulation, and the model is tested in a small network. Those issues are addressed in [9] and [10]. In [9] a decentralized model for a collaborative operation of microgrids (MGs) with the utility grid is investigated, considering technical constraints

and restricting batteries to either charge or discharge at each slot time, and propose a Benders decomposition method to manage users' private information.

On the other hand, in [10], an optimization algorithm based on the Alternating Direction Method of Multipliers (ADMM) is proposed to address day-ahead operational planning of a grid-connected local energy community preserving the users' information. The model in [10] is decomposed into two stages such that the first stage minimizes the cost of buying energy to the utility grid, and the second stage

minimizes the internal losses considering the line resistance and the voltage level.

Community-based energy markets have also been addressed from other disciplines. A game-theoretic approach under a cooperative structure is investigated in [11, 12, 13, 14] and the non-cooperative structures in [15, 16, 17] to model the P2P energy market. They generally focus on studying users' incentives to trade energy between them. The main results show that the TE framework provides efficiency in the DERs use and increases community welfare. Likewise, a Continuous Double-Auction (CDA) mechanism is widely used in the literature to establish the LEM price for the bids and asks (see, e.g., [4, 18, 19, 20]). However, to the best of our knowledge, under a P2P energy trading scheme, no work considers the voltage levels and the reactive power in the formulation, which are critical factors to maintain the network balanced (see, e.g., [21, 22, 23, 3, 24]).

The previous literature focuses on modeling trading energy markets between prosumers and consumers under a wide range of different assumptions and constraints and developing efficient algorithms to find reasonable quality solutions for the resulting models, providing valuable knowledge about these new markets. However, they do not consider the inherent uncertainties related to energy generation and consumption, which might impact the network efficiency and the community's social welfare.

1.1.2. Stochastic approaches

Contrary to deterministic approaches, stochastic models are recently gaining attention from scholars. Centralized markets under uncertainty have been investigated in [25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31]. Thus, an initial work is presented by [25] to address the uncertainty in energy trading markets through a hybrid stochastic/robust optimization model. The same approach is presented by [26] and [27] but using the General Nash Bargaining framework to decompose the original model into operational and bargaining problem. Authors in [28] use a stochastic approach to deal with the price uncertainty in the P2P energy market and avoid arbitrage by the users with the real-time market through a bi-level model based on a non-cooperative leader-follower game. Then, a two-stage robust optimization (RO) model is formulated by [29] to deal with uncertainties in a day-ahead and real-time spot market, maximizing the microgrids' profit and using the Benders decomposition approach for solving the resulting two-stage stochastic problem. Similarly, the RO approach is used by authors in [30] to manage the uncertainty marginal price in a P2P energy trading using the column-and-constraint generation (CCG) to decompose the robust model into subproblems. Likewise, the Markov decision process is used in [31] to solve a stochastic leader-follower P2P energy trading model under a game theory approach that considers social attributes.

On the other hand, decentralized markets with stochastic parameters have been studied in [32, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37, 38]. Specifically, authors of [32] propose a model to address the P2P energy traded, preserving the users' information and

covering the day-ahead and intraday market. A two-stage stochastic programming model is presented to manage the day-ahead market, such that the first stage variable includes the energy that the user is willing to trade in the real-time market, and in the second stage, the batteries operation is decided. The two-stage stochastic problem is decomposed into a set of stochastic subproblems, one for each user, and then solved through an ADMM algorithm. In [33] and [34] a distributionally robust co-optimization (DRO) model for the P2P energy trading and network operation of interconnected microgrids is presented. The energy requirement of each MG is managed in the first stage, and the strategy price is determined using an ADMM algorithm in the second stage. A similar strategy is proposed by [35] for users in a small-scale system using the RO approach and the ADMM to manage the privacy. In the same research line, [36] proposes a nested market clearing algorithm and a DRO approach to clear the market and manage the prosumers' behavior, respectively, where the ADMM is implemented to solve the DRO and preserve user privacy.

However, few articles have explored alternative methods of the well-known ADMM to decompose the stochastic models and manage user privacy under a non-centralized energy trading scheme. Authors in [37] propose a stochastic cartel nonlinear model which is decomposed using a surrogate Lagrangian relaxation method, and the work presented by [38] provides an enhanced Benders decomposition to manage the energy transaction in smart buildings. These two recently introduced methods extend the research line related to decomposition algorithms applied to manage decentralized energy trading schemes under uncertainty.

1.2. Research gap and contributions

The previous literature summarized deterministic and stochastic approaches to address P2P energy trading under different market schemes, where decomposition methods play a relevant role in modeling the users' interaction and managing their private information. However, most articles do not restrict BESS to simultaneously avoid the charging and discharging process because most do not include the network limitations. This unrealistic assumption generally simplifies the decomposition method application sacrificing the model accuracy. On the other hand, a common assumption in the above works is that all users possess a storage system to allow a flexible response to the load and generation forecast when a day-ahead and intraday market are considered. However, this assumption reflects another unrealistic situation because a community market is expected to be composed of consumers and prosumers, where prosumers have self-generation and/or a storage system and not necessarily both. Likewise, some reviewed articles define a fixed set of sellers (prosumers) and buyers (consumers) to implement game theory approaches. However, it is expected that in an energy trading framework, users with DERs can sell or buy energy in the LEM depending on their consumption and not always belongs to the sellers' group.

In addition, the formulations available in the literature rarely are tested under a significant number of agents, and only in few models consider the voltage stability and the reactive power, which prevents proving the models' scalability and their real application. Even the models that include these variables ([10],[32] and [33]) solve the resulting optimization model through the ADMM. However, the use of binary variables might complicate the convergence of this algorithm even by solving augmented dual Lagrangian problems. Likewise, the enhanced Benders decomposition algorithm proposed by [38], which is the closest to what is presented in this article, defines a fixed group of sellers and buyers to compete under the game theory approach and assumes that all the sellers have a storage system. Thus, motivated by the above discussion, our main contributions are presented as follows:

- A novel mixed-integer linear P2P energy trading model is presented based on two-stage stochastic programming, which considers i) the network technical constraints ii) traditional consumers and prosumers that act as buyers or sellers depending on their load consumption and self-generation, iii) saving the users' information partially, and iv) ensuring a fair energy transaction, i.e., preventing that a user buys and selling energy in the LEM simultaneously.
- The Strengthened Benders cuts, recently introduced in the literature, are implemented for the first time to address the binary variables belonging to the subproblems of a two-stage P2P energy trading problem in order to model the LEM users' interaction. Although the Benders decomposition algorithm is used in [9] to solve a similar deterministic problem, its approach considers a specific type of cutting planes generation, which might require high computational effort due to an explicit enumeration phase. By contrast, the Strengthened Benders cuts reduce the computational effort and address the binary variables related to the market and battery operation within subproblems.
- A numerical analysis is developed to identify the effect of the i) binary variables over the total energy traded in the LEM, ii) the battery operation over the individual profit when the global community cost is minimized in a two-stage P2P energy trading context, and iii) the batteries capacity to support a two-stage approach where the energy community compromises the entire energy buying and selling from/to the grid under unknown self-generation scenarios.
- A scalability assessment is developed in terms of the method convergence with respect to the time considering until 39 agents trading active power in DN of 69 nodes.

1.3. Article structure

The paper structure is summarized as follows. Section 2 defines the market design and presents the two-stage

programming formulation considering a centralized market to explain the market operation through the variables and equations. Section 3 explains the Benders decomposition algorithm to reduce the information shared by the end-users in the LEM under a distributed market design. The case study, the computational results, and further research are presented in Section 4. Finally, the conclusions are discussed in Section 5.

2. Problem definition

2.1. Market design

The authors in [3] and [4] establish three groups to categorize P2P energy trading models based on the interaction between the market players. Thus, in a centralized design, a coordinator decides the energy exchanged among users in the most cost-effective way, maximizing the community's social welfare. However, the customers play a passive role under this design, while the coordinator has full access to the users' assets and information (e.g., [39, 40, 41]). On the contrary, in a decentralized market design, the users have complete control over their devices, and they decide when to sell or buy; however, the total community efficiency is affected because the individual profit is prioritized over the community welfare (e.g., [43, 44, 45]). The distributed market design is the third group, and it is between the two above, where a coordinator provides accurate information about pricing and the community requirement, and the user decides when to sell/buy, generating better coordination between peers than decentralized design, improving the efficiency of the market (e.g., [46, 47]).

Based on the definitions presented in [3] and [4], this article covers the P2P energy trading scheme under a centralized and distributed market design. Thus, the community manager (CM) is defined as a coordinator between the agents, the distribution system operator (DSO), and the retailer in order to set the hourly energy imported (resp. exported) from (resp. to) the grid by the energy community in the day-ahead market. Specifically, the CM coordinates the energy traded in the LEM, considering the technical network constraints and identifying the energy surplus feed-in to the external grid or the energy bought to the retailer to maintain the system balanced at every time interval, as shown Fig. 1. Besides, the commodities traded in the local market include only the active power and not the reactive power; therefore, the CM also coordinates the reactive power required from the external grid to supply the reactive demand considering the voltage levels and the line capacities to avoid eventual network congestions produced by the energy exchanged between agents.

The substation connected to the slack bus is the energy exchange point between the external grid and the users. When the energy self-generated by the community is not enough to supply the total load, the retailer provides the remaining power at the same price for every agent. The users or agents considered in this paper might have a rooftop photovoltaic (PV) system or a storage device. Likewise, an agent with at least one of these technologies is a prosumer,

Figure 1: P2P energy trading schematic diagram modeled

which can trade energy between their neighbor and/or sell the energy surplus to the grid. On the contrary, a consumer is considered a user who only demands electricity. Finally, the prices used in this article correspond to i) the energy brought from the grid, which is a known parameter, ii) the feed-in tariff, which usually represents a fraction of the energy bought from the grid, and iii) the price of the energy traded in the local market, which is variable and in this paper is estimated through the Lagrange multipliers (used in [48, 49]) associated to the active and reactive power nodal constraints to identify the marginal cost to maintain the network balance.

2.2. Two-stage stochastic framework

The literature review in Section 1 showed that most P2P energy trading formulations are modeled from a deterministic approach, i.e., load consumption and PV generation are assumed to be known beforehand. However, these parameters are unknown under a day-ahead market context, and their wrong forecast could bring extra costs to the agents and the retailer. Therefore, in this article it is assumed that the exact value of these parameters is unknown. However, some information on their possible value is available through the probability distribution function, representing the uncertainty of a finite set of discrete scenarios \mathcal{S} , obtained by sampling from the continuous distributions of the random parameters. Thus, a scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$ corresponds to a possible realization of the energy prices, PV generation, and load consumption.

Under the previous uncertainty context, the two-stage stochastic programming approach appears as a suitable alternative for addressing the load/generation uncertainty and improving decisions regarding the hourly energy planning that the community will demand (resp. deliver) in the day-ahead market. Specifically, the two-stage stochastic approach defines two sets of decisions, which must be made in two different stages of the decision process. The first-stage decisions correspond to the “here-and-now” decisions that have to be made prior to realizing the stochastic parameters. In our P2P energy trading market, these decisions correspond to the lack/surplus energy from/to the grid to keep the system balanced. On the other hand, the second stage decisions correspond to the “wait-and-see” decisions that

can be postponed after realizing the stochastic parameters. These decisions can be seen as recourse actions undertaken to adjust the initial planning to the actual realization of energy consumption and PV generation. In this regard, the proposed two-stage stochastic approach aims to find day-ahead scheduling for the energy bought/sold to the grid that minimizes the global community cost. This approach leads to an equivalent deterministic mixed-integer linear program described in the next section.

2.3. Centralized model

The approach provided by this article allows the CM to coordinate the LEM operation under a distributed market design, i.e., without knowing the users’ information related to their consumption or DERs use. Nonetheless, we first introduce a centralized market design as a Mixed-Integer Linear Programming formulation (MILP), which will allow us to better explain the market operation before describing the methodology to provide a more active role for the users and reduce the information shared in the LEM.

Let κ_t^{bg} (resp. κ_t^{sg}) be the energy bought (resp. sold) from the grid at time period t . This variables’ definition leads us to the following objective function:

$$\text{minimize } z = \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \rho_s (\lambda_{t,s}^{bg} \kappa_t^{bg} - \lambda_{t,s}^{sg} \kappa_t^{sg}) \quad (1)$$

The objective function (1) minimizes the expected cost of the external network dependency through the first-stage variables, i.e., the total cost of the power injected and absorbed by the substation. The power provided by the grid (κ^{bg}) corresponds to the gap that the LEM cannot meet through the energy traded between peers, and the power absorbed (κ^{sg}) corresponds to the power surpluses generated by the DERs that is not stored in the batteries and is not traded in the LEM. Besides, $\rho_s \in [0, 1]$ is of the likelihood of occurrence the scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$ with $\sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \rho_s = 1$.

The following constraints bound the feasible solutions space through the network technical limitations, batteries behavior, and the LEM rules.

2.3.1. Network technical constraints

The formulation proposed in this article uses the optimal power flow (OPF) equations to include the network limitations. However, due to the high computational burden associated with the original AC-OPF problem applied to a two-stage stochastic programming problem, the following constraints have been already linearized using the approach developed in [50]. This linearization method has been selected because its convergence has been validated and tested in [51, 52, 53, 54], showing an error lower than 1.3% and requiring no additional network information. For other linearization methods, we suggest to the readers review the works in [55, 56, 57, 58]. In this regard, Eqs. (2) and (3) correspond to the balancing equations in every node for the active and reactive power, respectively. Specifically, the right-hand side of Eq. (2), which corresponds to the active power, depends on the type of bus. Thus, if the bus possesses an agent that trades energy in the community market, Eq. (2) considers from left to right: the power generated by the rooftop solar PV system (pg); the power discharged (ds) and charged (ch) by the battery, and the electricity load (PL). On the contrary, if the bus is the substation, Eq. (2) considers the power provided (κ^{bg}) and absorbed (κ^{sg}) by the substation. Thus, $\forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \forall s \in \mathcal{S}$:

$$v_{i,t,s}(G_i + \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{L}} G_{i,j}) + \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{L}} p_{t,s}^{i,j} = \begin{cases} pg_{i,t,s} + ds_{i,t,s} - ch_{i,t,s} - PL_{i,t,s} & \forall i \in \mathcal{A}, \\ \kappa_t^{bg} - \kappa_t^{sg} & \text{substation,} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Likewise, Eq. (3) considers the reactive power provided by the substation in every node, assuming that the distributed sources only generate active power. Thus, the reactive power (QL) is considered within the power flow equations affecting the line flow capacity, the voltage levels, and the angles, assuming that the external grid supplies the entire reactive power demand because the LEM only trades active power. Therefore, $\forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \forall s \in \mathcal{S}, \forall i \in \mathcal{B}$:

$$-v_{i,t,s}(B_i + \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{L}} (B_{i,j} - B_{S_{i,j}})) + \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{L}} q_{t,s}^{i,j} = q\kappa_{i,t,s}^{bg} - QL_{i,t,s} \quad (3)$$

Eqs. (4) correspond to the linearized line power flow equations, which do not present variation regarding [50]. Therefore; $\forall (i, j) \in \mathcal{L}, \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \forall s \in \mathcal{S}$:

$$G_{i,j} \left(\frac{\Delta v_{t,s}^{i,j}}{2} \right) - B_{i,j} (\Delta \theta_{t,s}^{i,j}) + LP_{i,j} = p_{t,s}^{i,j} \quad (4a)$$

$$-B_{i,j} \left(\frac{\Delta v_{t,s}^{i,j}}{2} \right) - G_{i,j} (\Delta \theta_{t,s}^{i,j}) + LQ_{i,j} = q_{t,s}^{i,j} \quad (4b)$$

Eqs. (4a) and (4b) manage the branch losses through a loss sensitive factor (LP and QL) that depends on the angle and the voltage. We refer the reader to [50] for a detailed explanation of the linearization methodology and the parameters introduced to handle the non-linearities and the loss factor.

The power injected by the rooftop PV system into the grid in Eq. (5a) must be lower or equal to the installed capacity multiplied by the parameter PG^{max} , representing the PV power normalized curve for every time t . Eq. (5b) limits the power provided and absorbed by the substation. Likewise, Eq. (5c) fixes the operational voltage ranges, and Eq. (5d) establishes the line's capacity. Therefore, $\forall s \in \mathcal{S}$:

$$0 \leq pg_{i,t,s} \leq PG_{t,s}^{max} DG_i \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{A}, \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (5a)$$

$$0 \leq \kappa_t^{sg}, \kappa_t^{bg} \leq \kappa^{max} \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (5b)$$

$$V^{min} \leq v_{i,t,s} \leq V^{max} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{B} \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (5c)$$

$$\sqrt{(p_{t,s}^{i,j})^2 + (q_{t,s}^{i,j})^2} \leq S_{i,j}^{max} \quad \forall (i, j) \in \mathcal{L}, \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (5d)$$

The quadratic expression in (5d) is linearized, converting the circumference into a regular polygon of \mathcal{R} sided (see, e.g., [42]) as follows:

$$A_{i,j}^r p_{t,s}^{i,j} + B_{i,j}^r q_{t,s}^{i,j} + C_{i,j}^r S_{i,j}^{max} \leq 0, \quad \mathcal{R} = \{1, 2, \dots, r\}. \quad (6)$$

2.3.2. Battery modelling

The following set of constraints models the battery behavior: Eq. (7a) represents the battery state of charge (SOC) for the next period, which depends on the current SOC plus (resp. minus) the energy-charged (resp. discharged) as appropriate. Eq. (7b) establishes the operational range of the battery multiplied by its installed capacity. Note that if an agent does not have a battery, its energy storage capacity is zero, forcing the other battery variables to zero. The formulation uses a binary variable to model the charge and discharge battery process because both actions cannot be executed simultaneously. Thus, Eq. (7c) represents the charging process, and Eq. (7d) the battery discharge. Therefore; $\forall i \in \mathcal{A}, \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \forall s \in \mathcal{S}$:

$$soc_{i,t+1,s} = soc_{i,t,s} + [\varphi^{ch} ch_{i,t,s} - \frac{1}{\varphi^{ds}} ds_{i,t,s}] \Delta t \quad (7a)$$

$$SOC^{min} BT_i \leq soc_{i,t,s} \leq SOC^{max} BT_i \quad (7b)$$

$$ch_{i,t,s} \leq PB(w_{i,t,s}) \quad (7c)$$

$$ds_{i,t,s} \leq PB(1 - w_{i,t,s}) \quad (7d)$$

2.3.3. Local energy market rules

Market constraints seek to identify the energy amount traded in the community market and the energy bought/sold to the grid for every agent. Thus, Eq. (8a) represents the relationship between the energy amount demanded and self-generated (left-hand side) and the energy traded in the LEM or bought/sold to the grid (right-hand side). However, to avoid an agent's purchase and sale of energy simultaneously, a binary variable (y) is introduced in Eqs. (8b) and (8c) to ensure that the energy selling occurs in the LEM only when the agent has an energy surplus (8b), or the energy purchasing occurs only when the agents require external energy to meet its electricity demand. (8c). i.e., if there is a power surplus, y takes value one and zero otherwise. Therefore; $\forall i \in \mathcal{A}, \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \forall s \in \mathcal{S}$

$$pg_{i,t,s} + ds_{i,t,s} - ch_{i,t,s} - PL_{i,t,s} - \epsilon_{i,t,s} = p_{i,t,s}^{sm} + p_{i,t,s}^{sg} + p_{i,t,s}^{bm} + p_{i,t,s}^{bg} \quad (8a)$$

$$p_{i,t,s}^{sm} + p_{i,t,s}^{sg} \leq M y_{i,t,s} \quad (8b)$$

$$p_{i,t,s}^{bm} + p_{i,t,s}^{bg} \geq M(y_{i,t,s} - 1) \quad (8c)$$

$$p_{i,t,s}^{bg}, p_{i,t,s}^{bm} \leq 0, \quad p_{i,t,s}^{sg}, p_{i,t,s}^{sm} \geq 0. \quad (8d)$$

In addition, to visualize the difference between the energy amount sold/bought to the market/grid, the Eqs. (9a) and (9b) are defined. Specifically, Eq. (9a) indicates that the total power sold to the grid must be equal to the energy absorbed by the substation, which combined with Eq. (8a) provides the energy sold in the LEM and to the grid for every user. Eq. (9b) homologous way is established the total power bought within the grid. Therefore; $\forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \forall s \in \mathcal{S}$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{A}} p_{i,t,s}^{sg} = \kappa_t^{sg} \quad (9a)$$

$$- \sum_{i \in \mathcal{A}} p_{i,t,s}^{bg} = \kappa_t^{bg} \quad (9b)$$

Note that Eqs. (9) match the energy amount provided by the DERs with the energy exported to the grid. This equality is possible because we introduce the ε variable in Eq. (8a) to manage the line losses. If ε is not defined, in Eq. (9a), the power sold by DERs would be greater than the exported to the grid, and in Eq. (9b), the power bought by the users would be lower than the total imported due to line losses. However, the ε variable introduction allows addressing the line losses and matching the energy traded in the LEM with the energy bought/sold from/to the grid.

Finally, the market balance equation is defined in Eq. (10) such that all the energy sold in the LEM is bought.

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{A}} p_{i,t,s}^{sm} + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{A}} p_{i,t,s}^{bm} = 0 \quad (10)$$

3. Distributed approach

In this section, the previous centralized model is reformulated into a distributed model to decrease the information shared by the users with the CM and increase the role of the prosumer in the LEM through an iterative scheme of supply and demand between users and the CM, considering at every moment the network limitations.

3.1. Preliminaries

The following equations must be rewritten to hide the agents' information from the CM when the previous formulation is addressed under a distributed perspective. To this end, we define in Eq. (11) the variable Δp (left-hand-side of Eq. 8a) to represent the difference between the load consumption and energy self-generated by the agents, modifying Eq.(2) as follows:

$$\Delta p_{i,t,s} = pg_{i,t,s} + ds_{i,t,s} - ch_{i,t,s} - PL_{i,t,s} - \varepsilon_{i,t,s} \quad (11)$$

$$v_{i,t,s}(G_i + \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{L}} G_{i,j}) + \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{L}} p_{i,t,s}^{i,j} = \begin{cases} \Delta p_{i,t,s} + \varepsilon_{i,t,s} & \forall i \in \mathcal{A}, \\ \kappa_t^{bg} - \kappa_t^{sg} & \text{substation,} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

Note that Eq. (12) hides the user load consumption, the energy self-generated by the PV systems, and the battery operation, providing to the CM only the information related to whether the users will operate as a generator or a consumer. Besides, as Δp includes ε variable, and Eq. (2) does not, the new Eq. (12) must add the ε variable to neutralize the Δp and maintain the equality defined in Eq. (2). Likewise, the Δp definition modify the equations (8) related to the LEM operation, such that Δp in Eq. (11) can take a positive value when the agent generates more energy than its electricity load (operate as a small generator) or take negative values in the opposite case, operating as a traditional consumer. Eq. (13a) reflects this situation opening up Δp into Δp^+ and Δp^- . Thus, in Eqs. (13b) and (13c), the power surplus (Δp^+) comprises the power sold to the market plus the power sold to the grid, and the power lack (Δp^-) includes the power bought from the market and the grid, respectively. Besides, to avoid simultaneous selling and to buy action by the agents, the logical constraints (13d) and (13e) ensure through a binary variable that the agents only sell energy when they have surplus; otherwise, they must buy energy from the market or the grid.

$$\Delta p_{i,t,s} = \Delta p_{i,t,s}^+ + \Delta p_{i,t,s}^- \quad (13a)$$

$$\Delta p_{i,t,s}^+ = p_{i,t,s}^{sm} + p_{i,t,s}^{sg} \quad (13b)$$

$$\Delta p_{i,t,s}^- = p_{i,t,s}^{bm} + p_{i,t,s}^{bg} \quad (13c)$$

$$\Delta p_{i,t,s}^+ \leq M(y_{i,t,s}) \quad (13d)$$

$$\Delta p_{i,t,s}^- \geq M(y_{i,t,s} - 1) \quad (13e)$$

In addition, the constraint (10) related to the total energy traded in the LEM must be rewritten in terms of variables known by the CM. Therefore, using Eqs. (9) and (13), Eq. (10) is rewritten as follows; $\forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \forall s \in \mathcal{S}$:

$$\kappa_t^{sg} - \kappa_t^{bg} - \sum_{i \in \mathcal{A}} \Delta p_{i,t,s} = 0 \quad (14)$$

3.2. The Benders decomposition approach (BD)

Once the users' information has been hidden through the Δp variable, the Benders decomposition approach is applied to separate the centralized model into a Master Problem (MP) related to the information known by the CM and SubProblems (SP), which address the users' information. The iterative methodology used in the BD algorithm allows for increasing the agents' participation in the LEM because they interact individually and continuously with the CM to respect the network constraints and minimize the expected global community cost as follows:

Users receive a suggestion from the CM regarding the partial information related to p^{bg} , p^{sg} , and Δp , which initially respect the network technical limitation (MP solution). Then, the users individually take the CM suggestion and minimize the power bought from the grid depending on its power generation, battery operation, and load consumption, and return new values for p^{bg} , p^{sg} and Δp (SP solutions), which are taken by the CM and verified if the currents values respect the network technical constraints. If these new values do not respect the network limitations, then the CM suggests a new consumption plan, taking into account the previous

information provided by the users. This iterative process occurs until it converges to a solution, which minimizes the cost of energy required from the grid and respects all network technical constraints.

It is worth remarking that the CM partially knows the users' information through the p^{bg} , p^{sg} and Δp . This information is crucial for the CM to manage and keep the network balanced. Nonetheless, this information is only partial because it does not provide the power generated by its DERs, their consumption, or the battery operation, guaranteeing users autonomy and privacy. Thus, the MP and the SPs are defined as follows:

3.2.1. Master problem

Let $Q_i(\cdot)$ be a recourse function that represent the cost of the agents i given the MP decisions $\Delta p, \epsilon, p^{bg}, p^{sg}$. Thus, the MP is bounded through the network limitation, and it is defined as follows:

$$\min \sum_{i \in \mathcal{A}} Q_i(\Delta p, \epsilon, p^{bg}, p^{sg}) \quad (15)$$

subject to

- The network technical constraints (3), (4) and (12).
- The voltage and lines capacity (5b)-(5d), and (6).
- The global LEM necessities (9).
- The LEM balancing (14).

3.2.2. Subproblems

Given the MP solution $\Delta p, \epsilon, p^{bg}, p^{sg}$, we now define a set of SPs, one for each agent. Thus, for each $i \in \mathcal{A}$, we have the following SP:

$$Q_i(\Delta p, \epsilon, p^{bg}, p^{sg}) = \min \sum_{i \in \mathcal{T}} \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \lambda_{i,t,s}^{bg} p_{i,t,s}^{bg} - \lambda_{i,t,s}^{sg} p_{i,t,s}^{sg} \quad (16)$$

subject to

- The users' consumption and battery operation (11), (5a), (7), and (13).

Each SP thus focuses on defining a plan for its own power generation, battery operation, and load consumption based on the power levels from the external grid imposed by the MP.

Note that usually, in a Benders decomposition, integer constraints are included in the MP. However, integer constraints related to battery operation and LEM rules are the SPs in our case. This poses the following issue, classical Benders cuts rely on the linear relaxation of SPs and, hence, it does not consider the integrality of the decision variables; this might lead to non-implementable solutions. Therefore, we propose to use a recently introduced type of cut, called Strengthened Benders' cuts (see [59] and [60]). These cuts rely on a Lagrangian relaxation of SPs, allowing us to guarantee the feasibility of integer constraints.

3.2.3. Strengthened Benders' cuts

This family of cuts is based on the observation that a valid cut can be generated by solving a Lagrangian relaxation, where the corresponding Lagrangian multipliers are fixed to the dual solution of the linear relaxation. Therefore, Benders' cuts can be strengthened by solving a mixed-integer program rather than only a linear program. Thus, in order to generate a Strengthened Benders' cut, we must first reformulate each SP by introducing the following variables: $\Delta \bar{p}_{i,t,s}, \bar{\epsilon}_{i,t,s}, \bar{p}_{i,t,s}^{bg}, \bar{p}_{i,t,s}^{sg}$ for each $i \in \mathcal{A}, t \in \mathcal{T}, s \in \mathcal{S}$. Thus, for each $i \in \mathcal{A}$, we reformulate the SPs as follows:

$$Q_i(\Delta p, \epsilon, p^{bg}, p^{sg}) = \min \sum_{i \in \mathcal{T}} \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} (\lambda_{i,t,s}^{bg} \bar{p}_{i,t,s}^{bg} - \lambda_{i,t,s}^{sg} \bar{p}_{i,t,s}^{sg}) \quad (17a)$$

$\forall t \in \mathcal{T}, s \in \mathcal{S}$ subject to

$$\Delta \bar{p}_{i,t,s} = \Delta p_{i,t,s} \quad (17b)$$

$$\bar{\epsilon}_{i,t,s} = \epsilon_{i,t,s} \quad (17c)$$

$$\bar{p}_{i,t,s}^{bg} = p_{i,t,s}^{bg} \quad (17d)$$

$$\bar{p}_{i,t,s}^{sg} = p_{i,t,s}^{sg} \quad (17e)$$

$$\Delta \bar{p}_{i,t,s} = p g_{i,t,s} + d s_{i,t,s} - c h_{i,t,s} - P L_{i,t,s} - \bar{\epsilon}_{i,t,s} \quad (17f)$$

$$\Delta \bar{p}_{i,t,s} = \Delta p_{i,t,s}^+ + \Delta p_{i,t,s}^- \quad (17g)$$

Constraints (5a), (7), (13b) – (13e).

Note that the constraints (11) and (13b) are rewritten with respect to the redundant variables $\Delta \bar{p}_{i,t,s}$ and $\bar{\epsilon}_{i,t,s}$ as (17f) and (17g), respectively. Although variables $\Delta \bar{p}_{i,t,s}, \bar{\epsilon}_{i,t,s}, \bar{p}_{i,t,s}^{bg}, \bar{p}_{i,t,s}^{sg}$ and constraints (17b)-(17e) are redundant for the SP_{*i*}, they play a key role in the generation of Strengthened Benders' cuts used to approximate the recourse functions. We refer the reader to [59] and [60] for more detail about these cuts family. Constraints (17b)-(17e) are then dualized leading to the following relaxed SPs:

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{Q}_i(\Delta p, \epsilon, p^{bg}, p^{sg}) = \min \sum_{i \in \mathcal{T}} \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} & \lambda_{i,t,s}^{bg} \bar{p}_{i,t,s}^{bg} - \lambda_{i,t,s}^{sg} \bar{p}_{i,t,s}^{sg} \\ & + \pi_{i,t,s}^{\Delta} (\Delta \bar{p}_{i,t,s} - \Delta p_{i,t,s}) + \pi_{i,t,s}^{\epsilon} (\bar{\epsilon}_{i,t,s} - \epsilon_{i,t,s}) \\ & + \pi_{i,t,s}^{bg} (\bar{p}_{i,t,s}^{bg} - p_{i,t,s}^{bg}) + \pi_{i,t,s}^{sg} (\bar{p}_{i,t,s}^{sg} - p_{i,t,s}^{sg}) \end{aligned} \quad (18a)$$

subject to:

$$\text{Constraints (5a), (7), (13), (17f), (17g).} \quad (18b)$$

Where π^{Δ} , π^{ϵ} , π^{bg} and π^{sg} are the Lagrange multipliers of the constraints (17b), (17c), (17d) and (17e), respectively.

Note that, by relaxing Constraints (17b)-(17e), the resulting SPs (18a)-(18b) are always feasible because variables $\Delta \bar{p}_{i,t,s}, \bar{\epsilon}_{i,t,s}, \bar{p}_{i,t,s}^{bg}, \bar{p}_{i,t,s}^{sg}$ are now free to balance Constraints (5a),(7), (13), (17f),(17g).

Let $\psi_j(\cdot)$ be the approximation of the recourse function $Q_i(\cdot)$ available at iteration j of the BD algorithm, which is defined by the set of supporting hyperplanes generated until iteration j . Thus for each $i \in \mathcal{A}$:

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_i(\Delta p, \varepsilon, p^{bg}, p^{sg}) = \min\{\eta_i : \eta_i \geq v_i^k - \\ \sum_{i \in \mathcal{T}} \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \pi_{i,t,s}^{\Delta,k} \Delta p_{i,t,s} - \pi_{i,t,s}^{\varepsilon,k} \varepsilon_{i,t,s} - \pi_{i,t,s}^{bg,k} p_{i,t,s}^{bg} - \\ \pi_{i,t,s}^{sg,k} p_{i,t,s}^{sg} \quad \forall k \in \{1, \dots, j-1\}\}. \end{aligned} \quad (19a)$$

Where

$$\begin{aligned} v_i^k = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{T}} \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \lambda_{i,t,s}^{bg} \bar{p}_{i,t,s}^{bg,k} - \lambda_{i,t,s}^{sg} \bar{p}_{i,t,s}^{sg,k} + \pi_{i,t,s}^{\Delta,k} (\Delta \bar{p}_{i,t,s}^k) \\ + \pi_{i,t,s}^{\varepsilon,k} (\bar{\varepsilon}_{i,t,s}) + \pi_{i,t,s}^{bg,k} \bar{p}_{i,t,s}^{bg,k} + \pi_{i,t,s}^{sg,k} \bar{p}_{i,t,s}^{sg,k}, \end{aligned} \quad (19b)$$

and $\pi_i^{\Delta,k}, \pi_i^{\varepsilon,k}, \pi_i^{sg,k}, \pi_i^{bg,k}$ are the coefficients of the cut generated at iteration $k < j$ by solving the Lagrangian relaxation (18a)-(18b). This leads to the following MP reformulation:

$$\min \sum_{i \in \mathcal{A}} \eta_i \quad (20a)$$

Subject to

$$\text{Constraints (5b) - (5d), (9), (3) - (6), (12), (14).} \quad (20b)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \eta_i \geq v_i^k - \sum_{i \in \mathcal{T}} \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \pi_{i,t,s}^{\Delta,k} (\Delta p_{i,t,s}) - \pi_{i,t,s}^{\varepsilon,k} (\varepsilon_{i,t,s}) \\ - \pi_{i,t,s}^{bg,k} p_{i,t,s}^{bg} - \pi_{i,t,s}^{sg,k} p_{i,t,s}^{sg} \quad \forall k \in \{1, \dots, j-1\}. \end{aligned} \quad (20c)$$

Thus, at each iteration of the BD algorithm, the MP is solved with a current approximation of the recourse functions. Its output is a feasible plan for the network, which consists of each agent's power levels from the external grid. Then, the approximation of the recourse functions is further improved by solving the SPs and generating a new linear cut.

3.3. Cut strategy

Note that in order to generate a Strengthened Benders' cut, we must solve the SPs (18a)-(18b) with a fixed dual solution, i.e., $\pi^\Delta, \pi^\varepsilon, \pi^{sg}, \pi^{bg}$ are fixed. These values can be arbitrarily chosen and then improved through a sub-gradient algorithm. However, it entails solving a series of mixed-integer linear programs for each SP, which might be computationally demanding. An alternative is to solve the linear relaxation of SPs (5a),(7), (13),(17a)-(17g) and set the variables $\pi^\Delta, \pi^\varepsilon, \pi^{sg}, \pi^{bg}$ to the dual values of corresponding Constraints (17b)-(17e), which entails only solving a linear and mixed-integer linear program for each SP. Note that the resulting mixed-integer linear programs are always feasible due to the relaxation of the copy constraints (17b)-(17e); however, this is not the case of the linear programming relaxation of each SP. We thus must consider the case of the linear relaxation of SPs (5a),(7), (13),(17a)-(17g) is infeasible due to the MP solution does not give them enough flexibility to satisfy the energy demand. To tackle this issue, we introduce an auxiliary variable ζ that allows us to balance

equation (17f) when necessary. For this purpose, the variable ζ is penalized in the objective function with a large enough coefficient, i.e., $\bar{M} \gg \lambda^{bg}$ and, hence, variables ζ only take a positive value when the demand in constraints (17f) cannot be satisfied by the energy production, the stock energy on the battery or the assigned energy from the retailers.

This reformulation and cut strategy have two main advantages. First, it guarantees that SPs are always feasible and, hence, we can compute an upper bound of the centralized problem by solving SPs (5a),(7), (13),(17a)-(17g) at any iteration of the BD algorithm. Second, we can use the Strengthened Benders' cuts to under-approximate the recourse functions. This approach is computationally advantaged as its only requests to solve the linear relaxation of each SP and the corresponding Lagrangian relaxation at each iteration of the Benders algorithm.

Note that the convergence to an optimal solution of the algorithm is no longer theoretically guaranteed due to the use of Strengthened Benders cuts and the fact that MP variables $\Delta p, \varepsilon, p^{bg}, p^{sg}$ are not restricted to be binary (see [60] for further details on this matter). Nonetheless, as this approximation leads to a significant reduction of the computational effort required at each iteration of the algorithm, it may positively impact the solution quality in practice (see, e.g., [61] and [62]). In addition, the algorithm provides both a valid feasible solution (upper bound) for the problem and a lower bound given by the approximation of the recourse functions in the master problem. Thus, the quality of the solution, concerning the optimal solution, can be measured through the gap between these solutions.

3.4. Summary

As a synthesis, the main steps of the proposed BD algorithm applied to the stochastic LEM problem are summarized in Algorithm 1.

4. Computational results

This section assesses the centralized and distributed approaches in a low-voltage DN, considering different scenarios and load profiles. The algorithm convergence and its time operation are analyzed and contrasted with the single centralized formulation. Likewise, different agents' numbers participating in the LEM are considered to measure the algorithm scalability. Besides, it is analyzed how the flexibility provided by the batteries allows the community to compromise the total energy bought or sold to the grid in a day-ahead market scheme.

4.1. Case study parameters

The 69-bus distribution system containing 68 branches and 40 loads is used to test the mathematical approaches. The peak active and reactive power has been modified to consider only residential profiles to address a small residential community market appropriately. Specifically, the peak loads oscillate between 2-5 [kW], and the reactive power maintains the original proportion concerning the active power. Fig 2 shows the test system with the loads distribution identifying

Algorithm 1: Benders algorithm

```

1 Initialize  $LB \leftarrow -\infty, UB \leftarrow +\infty, k \leftarrow 0$ 
2 while no stopping criterion is satisfied do
3   Solve the master problem (20a)-(20c)
4   Collect master solutions  $\Delta p_{i,t,s}, \varepsilon_{i,t,s}, p_{i,t,s}^{bg}, p_{i,t,s}^{sg}$ 
5   Update the lower bound  $LB = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{A}} \tilde{\eta}_i$ 
6   for  $i \in \mathcal{A}$  do
7     Solve the linear relaxation of
       subproblem (5a),(7), (13),(17a)-(17g) for
       agent  $i$ , fixing the corresponding master
       solution.
8     Collect the dual values
        $\pi_i^{\Delta,k}, \pi_i^{\varepsilon,k}, \pi_i^{bg,k}, \pi_i^{sg,k}$  of
       Constraints (17b)-(17e).
9     Solve the Lagrangian relaxation (18a)-(18b)
       with current approximation  $\psi_i(\cdot)$  and
       fixing the corresponding dual values.
10    Collect the redundant variables  $\bar{p}^{bg}$  and  $\bar{p}^{sg}$ 
        and the cut coefficient  $v_i^k$ .
11  end
12  Update the upper bound
        $UB = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{A}} \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \lambda_{t,s}^{bg} \bar{p}_{i,t,s}^{bg} - \lambda_{t,s}^{sg} \bar{p}_{i,t,s}^{sg}$ 
13  Add the Strengthened Benders' cuts to the
       master problem.
14   $k \leftarrow k + 1$ .
15 end

```

the users with PV and storage systems, in which the PV systems capacity is 20% greater than the peak active load, and for BESS, an 80% greater than the maximum electricity demand. The case study includes 39 agents, of which seven agents are traditional consumers without self-generation, five possess PV systems, and the remaining agents have hybrid PV-battery systems.

The total electricity load reaches up to 139 [kW], the reactive power to 99.2 [kvar], the total PV power installed to 177 [kW], and the total battery capacity to 309 [kWh] with an efficiency of 85% - 87% in the charging and discharging process (see Table 1). Note that the high BESS penetration allows facing the two-stage stochastic problem nature.

The curves shown in Fig 3 and Fig 4 correspond to three scenarios of 24 hours obtained from annual data with a timeslot of one hour. Specifically, Fig. 3 shows the twenty-three different residential load profiles [63] used to highlight the benefits of operating under a P2P energy trading scheme. The first scenario possesses the higher total load with 991.98 [kWh] and peak power of 59.98 [kW], followed by the second scenario with 842.23 [kWh] and peak power of 53.5 [kW], and the third case with 807.51 [kWh], and 505.59 [kW] of peak power.

On the other hand, Fig. 4 provides the aggregated load curves considering the thirty-nine agents together with the normalized curve of PV power generation [64] and the energy prices [65]. Likewise, the first scenario considers a

Figure 2: Modified IEEE 69-bus distribution network.

Table 1
Load and DERs parameters

Bus	PL	QL	PV	BT	Bus	PL	QL	PV	BT
6	5	4.23	7.5	15	33	3	2.14	4.5	0
7	4	2.97	6	12	34	3	4.42	4.5	9
8	4	2.88	6	12	35	3	2	4.5	9
9	4	2.93	0	0	36	2	1.43	0	0
10	3	2.04	4.5	0	37	4	2.85	6	12
11	5	3.59	7.5	15	39	4	2.83	6	12
12	3	2.15	4.5	9	40	5	3.54	7.5	15
13	5	3.13	7.5	15	41	2	1.67	3	6
14	5	3.44	7.5	15	43	2	1.43	3	0
16	4	2.64	6	12	45	4	2.68	6	12
17	3	1.75	0	0	46	2	1.34	3	6
18	2	1.17	3	6	48	3	2.14	0	0
20	2	1.2	3	6	49	2	1.43	3	6
21	5	3.55	7.5	15	52	2	1.2	3	6
22	3	2.1	4.5	0	54	5	2.9	0	0
24	3	2.14	4.5	9	59	3	2.5	4.5	9
26	5	3.57	7.5	15	61	4	2.7	6	12
27	3	2.14	4.5	9	64	4	3.1	6	12
28	4	2.86	6	12	66	4	2.8	6	0
29	4	2.86	0	0	68	2	0.8	3	6

total PV generation of 872.08 [kWh], which is the higher generation with a peak power of 177 [kW] at 13 hours, followed by the second scenario with a total generation of 770.48 [kWh] with a peak power of 123 [kW], and the third scenario in 24 hours generates 734 [kWh] with a peak power of 99.12 [kW] at 14 hours. Therefore, considering the load consumption and the PV generation described above, the PV systems provide 87.91 % of the total load in the first scenario, followed by the second scenario with 91.48 % and 90.9 % for the third scenario. Thus, the first scenario is the most demanding, followed by the second and the third.

4.2. Algorithm convergence and scalability assessment

This section presents the algorithm convergence results and addresses the model scalability. It is worth remarking that the algorithm based on Benders decomposition pretends to reduce the information provided by the agents to the CM

Figure 3: Overlapped residential load profiles for three different scenarios.

Figure 4: Scenarios for the energy prices, the PV power generation, and the aggregated residential loads.

rather than reduce the computational time from the centralized model. However, the following assessment measures the cost of reducing the shared information in terms of execution time.

Fig 5 shows the algorithm convergence for different amounts of agents participating in the LEM, considering the optimal value from the centralized model as a reference. Besides, every case indicates the algorithm running time, considering 2 hours as stop criteria. The execution time for the centralized model is not reported in Fig 5, but its time is lower than the algorithm, such that for three agents, the centralized formulation takes 22.8 [s] and 11 [min] for 39 agents. Likewise, considering a maximum running time of two hours, the algorithm converges to the optimal value until 16 agents participate in the LEM. Thus, the algorithm overcomes the maximum running time when the number of agents beats this value.

The average execution time involved at every iteration for the MP and SPs is reported in Table 2 to improve the understanding of the significant running time increases when many agents are willing to trade energy in the LEM. Thus, the SPs do not show a significant increase in terms of running time since considering 39 agents, the time required to solve the SPs is, on average lower than one second. However, every MP increases its execution time significantly from 1 [s] to 75 [s] on average when the users' numbers increase. This extra computational burden is explained because the MP includes the technical network constraints and extra constraints added in each iteration of the algorithm due to the Benders cuts.

Therefore, the results show an algorithm based on the Benders cuts that allow reducing the user information shared

Figure 5: Algorithm convergence

Table 2

Average algorithm running times by iteration

Agents number	3	4	8	16	25	39
MP [s]	1.091	1.338	5.265	15.01	38.58	75.29
SP [s]	0.042	0.049	0.098	0.20	0.37	0.67

in LEM, converging to the optimal value given by the centralized model, where the user information is public. In other words, The proposed algorithm reduces information shared between the agents without reducing the community welfare. These results are relevant because the findings reported in [35] for a similar market trading model indicate that the ADMM algorithm is far from the centralized model by 3%. In addition, other alternative mechanisms recently published in the literature like the surrogate Lagrangian relaxation in [37] and an enhanced Benders decomposition in [38] show that these alternative decomposition methods could provide a competitive performance as compared to the one reported by the ADMM under a P2P energy trading framework. In this sense, the convergence results of the algorithm reported in this article are aligned with the recent research.

4.3. Numerical results

This section presents the results considering the scenarios described in the previous section for the thirty-nine agents. Thus, Table 3 shows the aggregated results in kWh such that the energy bought and sold to the grid is the same for the three cases due to are the first-stage variables, which are minimized in the objective function. The second-stage variables corresponding to the battery behavior and the energy traded in the LEM show a lower battery and energy

Table 3
Global energy share for the three different scenarios

	Variable	Scn 1	Scn 2	Scn 3
Electricity Load	PL	991.981	842.233	807.511
PV generation	pg	872.11	770.22	733.28
BT discharge	ds	338.35	539.56	518.54
BT charge	ch	274.68	523.88	499.51
Energy bought to the grid	κ^{bg}	431.73	431.73	431.73
Energy sold to the grid	κ^{sg}	375.52	375.52	375.52
Energy traded in the LEM	p^{bm}	331.2	427.2	341.2
Losses		33.96	34.79	35.54

Figure 6: Energy share for a case (A) under a P2P energy trading scheme, (B) without Energy trading, (C) considering energy trading but linear batteries, and (D) Energy trading such as batteries and the market trading are linear variables.

traded share in the first scenario than the others because the first one is the most demanding. The remaining two scenarios have higher battery participation and more energy traded in the LEM because the batteries must charge or discharge the surpluses energy committed to buying/selling to the grid in the first stage, which is also traded in the market.

4.4. Model assessment under different assumptions

Four cases have been considered to visualize the P2P energy trading operation effects on the traditional scheme without trading. Specifically, case (A) corresponds to the DN operating under a P2P energy trading scheme. Case (B) is the same DN, but without energy trading, i.e., the prosumers sell their energy surplus to the primary grid, and the traditional consumer must buy all their demand to the external grid. Case (C) is similar to Case (A), but the battery can charge or discharge simultaneously through linear variables. Case (D) is based on (A), but there are no binary variables in this case, which means that the agents can sell/buy energy in the LEM or to the grid without first meeting their own consumption, and the battery can charge/discharge simultaneously. Thus, cases (C) and (D) aim to observe the distortion produced over the energy traded in the LEM when the binary variables are not included in the formulation, while the main goal between cases (A) and (B) is to quantify the improvements produced of operating under a P2P energy trading scheme.

Fig. 6 summarizes the results for the four cases for the three scenarios. Case (D) provides the most prominent results with energy traded in the LEM around 87% and 13% of the energy provided by the grid and a small energy share corresponding to self-consumption for the first and second scenarios. The absence of binary variables explains this irregular share compared with the other cases because there is no control to distinguish the energy to satisfy the load consumption and the energy traded in the LEM. After all, the agents are not restricted to meeting their electricity demand first to sell the energy surplus. Case (C), on the contrary of case (D), the energy traded in the LEM is on average 29% lower than case (A). This reduction is because the batteries take values between $[0,1]$, decreasing the power discharged/charged by the storage devices in this quantity and reducing their energy sharing from the total. Therefore, the improper use of the binary variables can significantly affect the energy amount traded in the local market, undervaluing or overestimating its real operation.

The results for case (B) do not directly impact the main grid dependence due to the high DERs penetration on the case study, but it does affect the community welfare. The community benefits of operating under a P2P energy trading scheme are discussed in detail later; however, it is worth stressing that the energy required from the grid decreased 21.2% regarding case (A), explained mainly with more energy bought in the cheapest hours and more energy trading in the highest hours compared with case (B).

4.5. Local energy market and batteries behavior

Fig. 7 provides a more detailed battery and market behavior by hours and scenarios. Specifically, the left-hand side shows every scenario's hourly aggregated charging and discharging battery process. As mentioned previously, the first scenario is the most demanding; therefore, the battery uses only in hours with high PV generation and high electricity prices. However, in the second and third scenarios, the batteries must provide the required flexibility to face the remaining energy bought to the grid because, in these scenarios, the load is lower than in the first case.

The right-hand side of Fig. 7 shows the hourly energy share from the grid, local market, and self-consumption. The positive grid values correspond to the power provided by the external grid, and the negative values, to the power sold to the grid. Likewise, the self-consumption concept includes the power generated by the PV systems and the power provided by the BESS. Thus, when the self-consumption takes negative values, it indicates more power charging the batteries than the generated by the PV systems.

For the three scenarios, the highest self-consumption corresponds to the hours with high PV generation, coinciding with the highest power sold to the grid. Besides, the LEM tends to occur during PV generation and the last day hours when the batteries start discharging because the electricity price is higher than the first hours.

Figure 7: Hourly market and battery behaviour

Figure 8: Local energy market pricing compared with the FIT and the grid price, corresponding to the third scenario

4.6. Local energy market pricing

Fig. 8 shows the LEM pricing paid by the users for the third scenario obtained from the dual variables corresponding to the nodal balance equations (2), which include the system losses. Thus, when agents do not have enough self-generation, the LEM price is almost equal to the energy from the grid. On the contrary, when the users have a high energy surplus, the LEM price equals the Feed-in tariff (FIT) option. However, when few agents have the energy capacity to trade in the LEM, the internal price is intermediate between the FIT and the grid price. Similar behavior occurs in the first and the second scenario.

4.7. Agents profits

The results of cases A (with energy trading) and B (without energy trading, only energy selling to the grid) have been contrasted to compare the agents' profits. The upper row of Fig. 9 shows the profit/cost value for every agent considering the three scenarios, where the orange line corresponds to case A, and the blue line represents Case B.

On the other hand, the lower row shows the net profit for every agent, which is the difference between the orange with the blue line.

The community welfare shows a slight increase when the agents are capable of trading energy. Specifically, in the first scenario, the benefits increase 17.7%, in the second scenario 18.2%, and 18.6% if the third scenario happens. However, some agents have a higher cost (negative values in Fig.9) when they trade energy than when they sell their surplus to the grid. This situation is explained because the model minimizes the total energy bought from the grid and does not maximize the individual profit. Specifically, since the market is modeled under a two-stage stochastic framework, some users with high battery capacity must use their storage to buy (charge) the extra energy committed in the first stage variables, generating a minimal extra cost (see second row Fig. 9).

It is worth noting that the individual profit analysis described above corresponds to a daily operational comparison between operating under a P2P energy trading scheme and not. i.e., the study is not an economic assessment of the long-term profitability of the P2P energy trading scheme. That economic assessment requires a separate researcher, and hence it is out of the scope of the Benders decomposition algorithm proposed in this article.

4.8. Future research and discussion

The previous section leaves implicitly introduced the question related to how to reduce the execution time related to the MPs and accelerate the algorithm convergence times. This issue has not been included within this article scope because its study requires a deep analysis separately. However, the baseline to compare future algorithm improvements or different decomposition methods like the column and

Figure 9: Agents profit comparison between using P2P energy trading or not for different scenarios

constraints generation has been established in the previous section.

The two-stage stochastic programming model formulation also could be extended or modified. For example, the formulation could include the reactive power provided by the DERs or measure the reactive power that the energy community could provide to the DSO as an ancillary service. The DSO entirely supply the reactive power in the current formulation; hence, this consideration could extend the model proposed. In this regard, it would be interesting to quantify the pricing for these local ancillary services markets and measure the economic incentive for the CM to manage and coordinate the user voltage/reactive power requirements. Likewise, the formulation could be extended to include the intraday market within the second stage variables and use the electric vehicles or demand response from the users to face the mismatches between the day-ahead and intraday market. Besides, the second-order cone programming approach could be implemented to address the non-linearities and non-convexity related to the network technical constraints and contrast the convergence and the running times with the model proposed in this article. In this regard, other decomposition methods like the well-known ADMM, the surrogate Lagrangian relaxation, or different variations of the Benders decomposition could be compared to study their efficiency.

In addition, the objective function presented in the formulation considers only first-stage variables related to the total energy bought/sold from/to the grid. However, in section 4, the results show that the individual profit is sometimes affected when the model is under a two-stage stochastic framework. Therefore, future works could include part of the individual cost in the objective function to mitigate these

events and avoid disincentives to trade energy in the LEM by users with high flexibility levels.

5. Conclusions

This paper proposes a two-stage stochastic programming model to represent an energy community operating in a day-ahead market under a P2P energy trading scheme. The benders decomposition method has been used to reduce the information provided by the users to operate in the LEM. A new family cut has been introduced in the decomposition method to manage the binary variables.

The 69-bus system has been used to contrast the model with the Benders algorithm considering from 3 to 39 agents trading energy under three scenarios of 24 hours, showing that variables related to users' simultaneous energy buying/selling and battery operations presented in the SPs, which prevent the classic Benders implementation. Thus, the proposed decomposition method uses the new Strengthened Benders cuts to converge to the same optimal value provided by the centralized model. i.e., the proposed methodology reduces the LEM's shared information without increasing the energy community cost. Besides, the non-use of binary variables to model the battery behavior or prevent the selling/buying energy simultaneously in the LEM underestimates or overestimates the energy traded in the community market, respectively.

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